

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

TESSe2b Demosites

Spain, Austria and Cyprus

The **TESSe2b** solution is already implemented in the 3 demosites. The monitoring to evaluate the energy performance of the houses will begin this month, with the first demosite (Barcelona) being inaugurated on February the 9th.

[Check out each one of TESSe2b demosites and stay tuned for more updates!](#)

Learn more about TESSe2b!
Don't miss the common workshop "Save today, use tomorrow", WSED2019, Wels, Austria (February 2019).
[Stay tuned for more updates!](#)

SPAIN Calonge de Segarra

10 Thermal Solar Collectors

4 PCM Tanks | 3 Cold PCM Tanks | 1 Domestic Hot Water Tank

Visit our website and find out more information about this innovative project.

[visit website](#)

AUSTRIA Kapfenberg

10 Thermal Solar Collectors

4 PCM Tanks | 1 Domestic Hot Water Tank | Free Cooling

CYPRUS Miliou Village

10 Thermal Solar Collectors

3 PCM Tanks | 3 Cold PCM Tanks | 1 Domestic Hot Water Tank

A 3D city model with a play button and social media icons. The text reads: "Residential Building Energy Storage by Solar and Geothermal Resources" and "Watch our video!".

Residential Building Energy Storage by Solar and Geothermal Resources

Watch our video!

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